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**Preservation and Enrichment: Indigenous Language of the IP
(Indigenous People) Tribes of Bukidnon in Pamplona,
Negros Oriental**

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The indigenous Bukidnon people of Pamplona, Negros Oriental, are part of a larger ethnic group primarily found in Mindanao, Philippines. While their original homeland is in the highlands of Mindanao, a smaller community has settled in the mountainous areas of Negros Island, particularly in Pamplona. The term "Bukidnon" translates to "people of the mountains" in Cebuano. Migration to the Visayas region, including Negros Oriental, likely occurred over centuries due to factors such as inter-tribal conflicts, land pressures, and colonial influences.

The objective of this research is to explore the current condition of the Indigenous Languages of the IP Bukidnon Tribe in Pamplona, Negros Oriental; identify the challenges faced in preserving these languages; and propose strategies to enrich them for future generations.

This study will utilize a descriptive-quantitative research design to assess the enrichment and preservation of the Indigenous Language of the IP Tribe Bukidnon in Pamplona, Negros Oriental. Descriptive research is employed to describe, evaluate, and record data related to the current status and practices concerning language preservation (Best, 2004). It interprets the natural characteristics of the community, including existing conditions, practices, and beliefs.

The quantitative aspect of the study will be used to determine and assess the level of awareness and language abilities of the respondents in Pamplona, Negros Oriental. Quantitative research focuses on the calculation of numerical data, and in this study, numerical data will be gathered through the use of questionnaires and surveys designed to measure the respondents' awareness and language skills.

The level of awareness among the residents of Pamplona, both overall and when categorized by gender, age, and location, has a descriptive interpretation of "high." This is likely because the language in question is their Mother Tongue. The level of proficiency

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in using the local dialect among the IPs (Indigenous Peoples) in Pamplona, both overall and when categorized by gender and age, has a descriptive interpretation of "very high." This indicates that the respondents use this dialect in their daily communication.

The level of awareness among men is higher than that of women, suggesting that men tend to think more deeply than women. However, in terms of proficiency in using the dialect, women score higher than men, indicating that women are more inclined to engage in conversation or speak compared to men. When categorized by age, the results show that older individuals have a better understanding and usage of their first language compared to the younger generation, who tend to adapt to modernization. This is often due to the prevalence of informal communication, such as the use of slang.

There is a significant relationship between awareness and proficiency, as an increase in the level of awareness corresponds to an increase in the level of proficiency. This suggests that when you understand a word, you are more likely to use it in any form of communication or conversation, leading to greater learning.

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